

SOCIAL PHOBIA IN YOUNG PEOPLE'S PERCEPTIONS OF FAMILY LIFE

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Annotation.

The formation of social phobia and its prevention in the imagination of young people about family life, the opinions of Uzbek scientists on preparing for family life and the issues of preparing young people for family life are covered. Key words: social phobia, anxiety, preparation for family life, opinions of scientists on preparation for family life.

The problem of preparing the young generation for family life in our Republic only in the years of independence, comprehensive attention was paid to it, along with the family of every citizen by schools, neighborhoods, educational institutions, public organizations Attention was paid to the responsibility and the level of public policy to the family problem rose.

It is known that the basis of a healthy family is the interaction of the husband and wife in the family relation to their children, their children's parents, brothers, sisters and other relatives, duties and responsibilities towards society.

Most of the young people have a family in their student years or at the end of it because of what they have built, in family-marital relations, in communication with family members high-level spiritual-ethical and pedagogical-psychological preparation, life they are required to have culture. Our observations show that most students are not yet ready to start such a relationship.

Family relations in the "Family Code" of the Republic of Uzbekistan is set. These are marriages, spouses, parents, children and other family members relations between members. That is why young people are the first to start a family they need to understand the concept of family and marriage, its essence. This includes, first of all, the fact that each citizen can be in only one marriage to occur with the consent of both parties, to personal and property equality to have, equal rights in obligations, protection of the family by the state protection and promotion of motherhood, mutual marriage and family, such as the legal regulation of relations by the state they are required to learn the rules and follow them.

Secondly, it is compulsory for every young person to get married voluntarily. It is important to know that marriage is prohibited in the "Family Code". Sociological monographs conducted in our republic on the age of marriage shows that it is starting a bit early. Family life of girls Physical, spiritual, mental, sexual unpreparedness is the following negative in family life causing consequences:

- divorces are increasing;
- the interval between women having children is decreasing;
- The health of women aged 17-20 is deteriorating;
- building a family leads to a decrease in opportunities;
- incompatibility of families where the boy and the girl are adults;
- cases of early family formation or late family formation of family life affecting its stability.

In addition to the above, only in preparing young people for family life attention is given to girls and boys are ignored. If the guy too if they are not ready for family life, the family they build will not be strong. So, young men are also morally high, have a wide range of ideas, and are polite it is also important to monitor your health. Girls as well as young men to check their health before marriage transferring the factors that cause the future breakdown of the family they have built helps prevent. For example, infectious or chronic of both ages if their illness is diagnosed as mental illness or mental weakness, their marriage is prohibited will be done. Allowing marriage between close relatives when starting a family not allowed. As a result of such marriages, disabled and mentally retarded children are born come and the family's happiness is suffering.

Many opinions have been expressed by Uzbek scientists about preparing young people for family life. V.M.Karimova has these ideas unique to representatives of different ages and genders way of life, education, experience of individuals and groups, while researching the dependence on profession, the socio-psychological position of the woman and man in the family, the influence of the couple on the upbringing of children in the family, right in young people, conditions for the formation of acceptable family and social concepts and psychological illuminates the factors. At the same time, marriage and family, age of marriage, Uzbek families national values, personal qualities that ensure family stability, characteristics of both sexes and the conditions of their manifestation in the family the status of men and women, the number of children, making them perfect in every way ideas about ways to bring up and involve in family work developed socio-psychological mechanisms related to the formation. G. B. Shoumarov also plays a key role in preparing young people for family life focus on

love, family, its characteristics, family problems, especially. Divorce, death of children, causes of childlessness, economic affairs not receiving, family upbringing problems, communicative tasks of family members, not being able to use free time correctly, the biological, psychological, social life, moral-psychological environment and those influencing it factors, relations between family members and their laws, sex focuses on the issues of the influence of education.

The main time of young people is studying and doing other public works passes with At first, peers, colleagues, communicates with leaders. At the time of entering into this conversation, when other people talk about their life, family difficulties, problems between husband and wife, mother-in-law, and relatives, unmarried girls have negative concepts, and they do not know or understand that family life is getting married. phobias are formed about it. and these social phobias make it difficult for us to get married. We know that what a person thinks in his mind is reflected in his life.

Even when getting married, negative thoughts about mother-in-law and husband lead to a bad marriage, which is social phobias, that is, we are afraid of things that have not happened in our lives and we have a negative attitude towards them.

Family and marriage issues are one of the most important problems today preparing young people for family life based on national values is also special is gaining relevance. Because young people are on the threshold of independent life on the one hand, they need to be ready for family life, on the other on the other hand, in preparing the young generation for family life in educational institutions they act as specialists. A row before young people when starting a family requirements are set, the most important of which are social, household, spiritual, to be mentally and sexually ready. In this field, sociologist, demographer, psychologists, pedagogues, scientists all prepare young people for family life focus on the following directions:

- focus on family harmony;
- compliance with the standards of moral and moral formation or behavior;
- introduction to the basics of the law on marriage;
- to be psychologically ready to start a family and overcome social phobias together with a psychologist, which will prevent family problems in the future;
- physiological and hygienic preparation;
- arming with pedagogical knowledge;
- formation of an aesthetic attitude to family life.

Preparing students for family life has its own characteristics and these are family traditions, learning about economic and household possibilities, healthy ability to create a psychological environment, family responsibilities and tasks with the demands of society to be able to harmonize, to create a model of the future family, to manage it consists of forming skills and competencies. As a result of social phobia of young people, first of all, young people who are about to start a family and young married families suffer. That's why today In order to improve the health of the society, it is especially necessary to be careful that young people fall prey to subconscious social phobias, and to protect them from this danger, it is necessary to guide them to fight consciously on the basis of providing them with deep knowledge.

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